

OG'ZAKI TESTNI QAYTA KO'RIB CHIQISH: OBYEKTIVLIK, ISHONCHLILIK VA TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.

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Annotatsiya

KIRISH: mazkur ishda xususiy til markazida ingliz tilini B1 darajasida o'rganayotgan talabalar uchun yakuniy og'zaki test tahlil qilinadi va takomillashtiriladi. Mavjud test amaliylik, ishonchlilik, validlik, autentiklik va qayta ta'sir (washback) mezonlari asosida baholangan. Tadqiqot natijalari testning amaliy va autentik ekanligini, biroq subyektiv baholash hamda sifatli fikr-mulohazalarning yetishmasligi sababli uning ishonchliligi va shaffofligi yetarli emasligini ko'rsatadi. Taklif etilayotgan modifikatsiya videomateriallardan foydalanish, strukturallashtirilgan intervyu, tayyorgarlik vaqtini uzaytirish hamda analitik baholash mezonlarini joriy etishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu esa baholashning obyektivligi va samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

MAQSAD: xususiy til markazida B1 darajasida ingliz tilini o'rganayotgan talabalar uchun yakuniy og'zaki testning sifat ko'rsatkichlarini tahlil qilish va uni takomillashtirish yo'llarini ishlab chiqish.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: tadqiqotda yakuniy og'zaki test amaliylik, ishonchlilik, validlik, autentiklik va qayta ta'sir mezonlari asosida tahlil qilindi. Baholashda qiyosiy va tahliliy yondashuvlardan foydalanildi.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: tadqiqot natijalari testning amaliy va autentik ekanligini ko'rsatdi. Biroq subyektiv baholash va sifatli fikr-mulohazalarning yetishmasligi uning ishonchliligi hamda shaffofligini pasaytirishi aniqlandi. Videomateriallardan foydalanish, strukturallashtirilgan intervyu va analitik baholash mezonlarini joriy etish baholash sifatini oshirishga xizmat qilishi belgilandi.

XULOSA: takomillashtirilgan og'zaki test modeli baholashning obyektivligi, ishonchliligi va samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tilni baholash, og'zaki nutqni baholash, validlik, ishonchlilik, qayta ta'sir, CEFR B1 darajasi, ingliz tilini o'qitish.

ПЕРЕОСМЫСЛЕНИЕ УСТНОГО ТЕСТА: ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ОБЪЕКТИВНОСТИ, НАДЕЖНОСТИ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ.

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Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в данной работе проводится анализ и модернизация итогового теста по говорению для изучающих английский язык на уровне B1 в частном языковом центре. Существующий тест оценивается с точки зрения практичности, надежности, валидности, аутентичности и обратного воздействия. Результаты показывают, что тест является практичным и аутентичным, однако недостаточно надежным и прозрачным из-за субъективного оценивания и отсутствия качественной

обратной связи. Предлагаемая модификация включает использование видеоматериала, структурированного интервью, увеличенного времени на подготовку и аналитической шкалы оценивания, что способствует повышению объективности и эффективности оценивания.

ЦЕЛЬ: проанализировать качество итогового устного теста для изучающих английский язык на уровне B1 в частном языковом центре и разработать пути его совершенствования.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: в исследовании итоговый устный тест был проанализирован по критериям практичности, надёжности, валидности, аутентичности и обратного воздействия. Используются аналитический и сравнительный подходы.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: результаты исследования показали, что тест является практичным и аутентичным. Однако субъективность оценивания и недостаток качественной обратной связи снижают его надёжность и прозрачность. Установлено, что использование видеоматериалов, структурированного интервью и аналитических критериев оценивания способствует повышению качества оценки.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: усовершенствованная модель устного теста способствует повышению объективности, надёжности и эффективности оценивания.

Ключевые слова: языковое оценивание, оценивание говорения, валидность, надёжность, обратное воздействие, уровень B1 CEFR, преподавание английского языка.

RETHINKING ORAL TESTING: ENHANCING OBJECTIVITY, RELIABILITY, AND LEARNING EFFECTIVENESS.

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Annotation

INTRODUCTION: this paper analyzes and redesigns a final speaking test for English language learners at the B1 level in a private language center. The existing test is evaluated in terms of practicality, reliability, validity, authenticity, and washback effect. The findings indicate that the test is practical and authentic; however, it lacks sufficient reliability and transparency due to subjective scoring and the absence of meaningful feedback. The proposed modification incorporates video-based materials, a structured interview format, extended preparation time, and an analytic rating scale. These changes are expected to enhance the objectivity, reliability, and overall effectiveness of the assessment process.

AIM: to analyze the quality of the final speaking test for B1-level English learners in a private language center and propose ways to improve it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the final speaking test was evaluated in terms of practicality, reliability, validity, authenticity, and washback. Analytical and comparative approaches were employed.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: the findings showed that the test is practical and authentic. However, subjective scoring and insufficient feedback reduce its reliability and

transparency. The use of video materials, structured interviews, and analytic scoring criteria was found to improve assessment quality.

CONCLUSION: the improved speaking test model contributes to greater objectivity, reliability, and effectiveness of assessment.

Keywords: language assessment, speaking assessment, validity, reliability, washback, CEFR B1 level, English language teaching.

One of the most important steps in teaching and learning processes is assessment. Sufficient, quality assessment engages students in the learning activities that are desired by the teacher (Brown & Glasner, 2003). According to Ramsden (2003), assessment is not only an integral part of teaching, but it is also an instrument that can assist in improvement of teaching.

Formative and summative are two purposes of the assessment that are generally recognized. Formative assessment provides learners with the information whether the learning strategies they are using are effective or not and on the learning process itself. Furthermore, teachers use this type of assessment to give a feedback during this learning process. Summative assessment usually occurs at the end of a course, instruction or unit when teaching and learning processes are completed. That is to say formative is an assessment **for** learning, whereas summative is an assessment **of** learning (Arends & Kilcher, 2010). Even though the purposes of these two types of assessment are different, “there is one similarity between formative and summative assessment: in both we match performance as it is, with performance as it should be” (Biggs & Tang, 2011, p. 196).

This paper intends to modify a summative assessment task – the final test for the B1 CEFR level English language students of the private language center after analyses of the existing test.

Critique of an existing language test/assessment

The center under scrutiny mostly applies Communicative Language Teaching and Headway Curriculum is used as the basis of the courses. Since the center promotes a student-centered approach to teaching where teachers are facilitators and guides who coach by directing, observing and advising, the additional materials from other sources including internet are also applied. Even though “teaching is not a matter of simply transmitting information, but engaging students in active learning, building their knowledge in terms of what they already understand” (Biggs & Tang, 2011, p. 22) for the Center, the speaking part of the Final Test does not suit the high standard that the center claims to adhere. Thus, it should be revised and modified.

The curriculum of the Intermediate Level (B1) sets the following goals or the learners aligned with the CEFR standards (Council of Europe, 2001):

The main goal is to prepare learners to deal with most situations likely to arise in an area where the language is spoken. Moreover, further goals include tasks that strengthen

students' language skills through discussions longer reading passages more detailed listening and extensive writing activities.

In order for student to be passed to the next level, the final result must be 80% or higher and is based on student's performance during formative quizzes, summative final test and attendance. Final Test weighs 20 % out of 100% which is a high stake testing unit in this program and the results might influence the final decision on the student's level. Based on the results the students will be assigned to either take the next level or retake the same level again. Throughout three months (that is the period that session lasts in the chosen center), students are exposed to all macro skills at different levels and the most emphasis is given to speaking. Students practice all skills and do all types of exercises on grammar and vocabulary. They take different quizzes on Grammar, Vocabulary, Reading, Listening, Speaking and are given Written assignments as homework.

The testing and teaching processes should be aligned to each other and work as partners (Hughes, 2003). Therefore, if students are exposed to speaking skill during their classes, then the test is to evaluate students' knowledge on it. Otherwise, according to Hughes (2003), "we are then likely to suffer from harmful backwash" (p. 2).

Since the main goal of the curricula is to develop oral proficiency of students, it has been decided to emphasize speaking in the final summative test. However, grammar and vocabulary are checked through the fill-in the gaps and matching exercises. The written part of the exam did not cause any problems to the participants, but the speaking part made them feel unsatisfied because they did not understand the principles of scoring and therefore, they felt that the grade was unfair. Moreover, even though students had talked about the topic discussed and it seemed a not very difficult theme, they did not have enough information on it to be able to speak freely in a very limited time – students were only given one minute to speak and no preparation time was offered. Students felt that the questions they were asked were too broad and, as a result, they could not answer them properly.

Let us look at the speaking part of the test more closely basing the critique on five major principles of assessment: practicality, reliability, validity, authenticity and washback.

According to Mousavi (2009), practicality involves the amount of time and money that the test takes to prepare and to conduct, easy way of scoring it and providing the results along with the feedback to students. The speaking part of the final test is easy to administer. All that the teacher needs to do prior the test is to print out a cue card which is "within budgetary limits" (Brown & Abeywickrama, 2010, p. 26) of the school. The time allocated for each student is approximately 5 to 7 minutes and considering the fact that it is a private language center with only 6 to 8 students in a class, it does not take much time. However, as stated above, 5 -7 minutes were not enough for my participant to give good thoughtful answers. The way teachers graded the test was very subjective and intuitive and therefore the teacher did not spend much time on scoring it. Besides that, the teacher did not provide any feedback which also saved time. As we can see, from the perspective of the school, we can consider the test practical.

Brown and Abeywickrama (2010) suggest that a reliable test should generate the same results when administered to different students (or the same students) at two different times. Taking into the account that the scorers of the test do not use any rubric but subjectively decide to grade students on the scale from 1 to 5, we can definitely say that the rater reliability is very low here for we cannot trust that after talking to several students and without having any specific criteria to grade it, a tester will “yield consistent scores of the same test” (Brown & Abeywickrama, 2010, p. 28). Since the student was not aware of what he was going to be graded on his already existing anxiety grew bigger and student’s performance was influenced negatively in this case. Taking into consideration all the above, the speaking final test cannot satisfy the requirements of the reliability principle.

One of the most complicated criterion of an efficient, adequate test is validity. Validity is the language assessment principle that measures “the extent to which inferences made from assessment results are appropriate, meaningful, and useful in terms of the purpose of the assessment” (Gronlund, 1998, p. 226). If talking about the test in terms of its purpose, then the test seems to be valid because it measures what it is supposed to measure that is speaking. Also, the topic of the test was covered during the course. Moreover, the course claims to be teaching communicative competence of students and as we can see in the description of objectives, it is being taught and mastered throughout the course. Therefore, the mode of the interaction (interview) chosen for the test corresponds with the objectives. The speaking test have content-related validity to some extent. However, construct validity is under question in this test because there is no grading rubric that can show whether the scoring was done in a proper way and final score for the interview does not include such factors as “pronunciation, fluency, grammatical accuracy or vocabulary use” (Brown and Abeywickrama, 2010, p. 33). Furthermore, the student’s understanding of the fairness of a test is an essential part of the learner’s performance. Since there was no prior explanation of the grading criteria and the feedback was not provided to the student, face validity is not being considered in this test design.

The next main principle of language testing is authenticity. Authenticity is one of the complex criterion that has been speculated on among scholars. Bachman and Palmer (1996) state that authenticity as “the degree of correspondence of the characteristics of a given language test task to the feature of a target language task” (p. 23). Target language use is a “situation or context in which the test taker will be using the language outside of the test itself” (Bachmann and Palmer, 1996, p. 18). All parts of the test use natural language. In the first part of the interview, the test-taker is asked personalized questions on his interests, family and study. The theme of the second part of the test is Internet. For teenagers and young adults, this topic is relevant, interesting and meaningful. According to Brown and Abeywickrama (2010), the test can comply with authenticity principle if the items of a test are connected to each other. The third part of the speaking test is a continuation of the Part 2 that also proves that the critiqued test is authentic.

After the test has been taken, there should be the effect of it on teaching and learning that Hughes (2003) called backwash. It can be harmful or beneficial. When talking about beneficial or positive influence of washback, Brown and Abeywickrama (2010) suggest that it “gives learners feedback that enhances their language development” (p. 38). Unfortunately, since the speaking test is final, teachers do not see the necessity to provide students with the feedback on it. The results are not justified and no guidelines for further improvement of weaknesses as well as praise on strengths are provided to students. Students are not motivated and they do not “gain a sense of accomplishment and challenge” (Brown and Abeywickrama, 2010, p. 39). Therefore, in terms of future development of student’s language proficiency and future improvement of teaching practices, the test does not provide a beneficial washback.

Overall, we can see the criticized Final test of a Private language center has its strengths in being practical, partially valid and authentic. However, the test should be modified in order to adhere to the following principles: reliability, validity, and enhance a positive washback on both the teacher and the learner.

The modified version of the test

In the real world, listening and speaking are integrated and it is very difficult to deal with oral production tasks without enhancing listening tasks (Brown & Abeywickrama, 2010). Therefore, one of the suggestions to improve the chosen speaking test is to add the video from YouTube as a trigger and suggestions for creative construction of the ideas. Another challenge that test designers can encounter is the techniques that can help to elicit the required forms or vocabulary. The test modification suggests to use more specific questions on the topic and the personalized questions on the topic in the follow-up section.

When assessing oral production there is a challenge of grading the task with the open-ended questions. In order to minimize the subjectiveness of the test, an analytical rubric (Appendix II) is offered as another modification to the existing test. In order to provide reliable test it is important to assign more than one grades with several features in our case they are: grammar and vocabulary, discourse management, pronunciation, and interactive communication (Brown & Abeywickrama, 2010). The offered grading is on the scale from 1 to 5 with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest grade. The last offered modification is the time allocated for the test. The length of the oral interviews can vary from 5 minutes to one hour (Brown & Abeywickrama, 2010). Considering the time for the video and preparing time for the second part, it is proposed to lengthen the time of the interview from 5 – 7 to 15 - 20 minutes as according to Hughes (2003), “it is unlikely that reliable information can be obtained in less than about 15 minutes” (p. 124).

The main speaking objective of the chosen center is the development of the ability to understand and interact successfully in English (Hughes, 2003). The format for the speaking test is an interview. The guidelines for the modified version of the speaking test are adopted from the suggested by Hughes (2003, pp. 124-126) framework:

- The allocated time is about 15 minutes for each test-taker.

- The test should be planned cautiously even though in the individual oral interview the procedures and questions could be adapted, it is important to have some plan that will be followed by the test-giver.

- More than one format and several items should be used during one test in order to avoid repetition or problems with the topic that a test taker might have.

- There will be two testers for the interview that can help not only with elicitation of performance but reliable scoring.

- Since the individual oral tests might be quite stressful and overwhelming for the learners, it is very important to create a comfortable relaxing environment and therefore the interview should be started with the easy questions about the name, region the test taker is from, etc.

- A tester should not talk much but provide the test taker with the sufficient time to answer questions or give explanations. If necessary explain one more time without lengthy repeated clarifications.

- Before the interview, the appropriate scoring rubric should be prepared and introduced to the language learners.

Original Speaking Test:

Part 1

- What's your name?
- Where do you come from?
- Where do you live?
- Are you married?
- How many brothers or sisters do you have?

Part 2

- Talk about Internet. Why and when do people use it? Should it be censored? If yes, why?

Taking into consideration the above stated, the below are my suggestions on oral test stages' modification based on the Canale's (1984) framework of the oral interview:

Modified version of the Final Test – Instructions.

This is your final speaking test. It will take approximately 15 minutes and will be given in the form of the interview. There are three parts. In the first part you will be asked to introduce yourself and a few general questions about the family, weather, study/work, hobbies or interests will follow. In part two you will be given a card with the topic that you have practiced in your lessons throughout 3 months. You will watch a short video and after that will have 3 minutes to prepare to answer questions in the Cue card. You can take notes while watching a video if necessary. After the time is up, you will be asked to talk on the topic for minimum 1-2 minutes without interruption. The third part consist of follow up questions on the topic from Part 2. Please relax, enjoy talking in English and try to talk as much as possible. Your final result will be based on the rubric (Appendix II) that was provided to you by your teacher last class.

Part 1:

Small talk and Level Check

Hello. How are you today?

What's your name?

Where do you come from?

What do you do in your free time?

Do you use Internet?

When was the last time you used the Internet?

When was the last time you had no internet access? What were you doing?

Have you ever met someone online and after that met them in person? Was the person like you expected him/her to be?

Part 2

You will watch a video "What is Internet?" (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Dxcc6ycZ73M>). The topic was covered during your lessons. Please take notes of what people say about the internet. After the video you will be provided with the card and prepare to talk for 2-3 minutes on the topic. The subtitles will be switched on for you.

Cue card:

Please prepare to talk for 2-3 minutes:

Why do we people need Internet?

What are benefits of the Internet?

What are the dangers of the Internet?

Should the internet be censored or regulated? Why? Or Why not?

Part 3 – The Follow up

Are you a part of any social networks like Facebook or Google?

When did you get your first email address?

What is your favorite website?

Part 4

Thank you very much.

This is the end of your Final Speaking Test.

You will be provided with the results the next lesson.

How are you feeling about the interview?

Do you have any questions to me?

The provided modified versions of the speaking part of the test can be considered reliable, authentic, valid, practical and there is a possibility to have a positive washback. Firstly, the test can be taken by the test taker within certain time limit and clear direction are provided to both the student and the tester/teacher. Secondly, in order to better use of the personnel, the test can be videotape and later graded by two or more testers/teachers. This way of grading can also ensure the rater- reliability and consequently the subjective grading of the test might be lowered (Brown and Abeywickrama, 2010). The modified speaking test evaluates student's speaking skills what is being one of the central parts of the curriculum of the Center. The tests assesses what it is supposed to be assessing that is an interactive speaking (Biggs & Tang, 2011). Considering the above stated we can say that the test is valid and reliable.

The modified version of the test can also be considered reliable because an analytic rubric is used to grade students performance across several criteria. Moreover, the students are introduced to the rubric beforehand and therefore they are aware on the scoring system. After the test has been taken and graded, the positive washback on both teaching and learning processes can occur due to the enough data for the teacher to provide a constructive feedback.

As in criterion-referenced assessment, assessment task should be aligned to the learning outcomes of the course. The learning outcomes identify the activities that students should be engaged into along with the content of the activity. The teachers' task is to provide a learning atmosphere that fosters the student's performance of the activities and assessment task and evaluate the performance in accordance with the learning outcomes (Biggs & Tang, 2011). The modified version stimulates students to perform better job because of the positive learning environment with the warm up questions in the beginning of the test and with the wrap-up questions on the students' feelings at the end as well as the scaffolding provided with the video on the topic of the speaking test.

According to the placement test, the participant of the project was assigned to the Intermediate level which is a B 1 level according to the CEFR. The questions are designed in a way to comply with the requirements in terms criteria described in *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: learning, teaching, assessment* (Council of Europe, 2001). Moreover, the topic of the test – the Internet – has been discussed in one of the lessons and, therefore, was not new or irrelevant to the student.

The modified version was piloted and the participant was asked to share his feeling toward both existing and modified versions. As it was described above, when taking the Existing version, Aziz got confused and felt very anxious because the process of testing seemed to be rushed though. Additionally, when receiving the grade on the last lesson of the semester, he felt unhappy and unsatisfied due to the lack of the criteria of grading and the feedback. When taking part in the modified version of the test, Aziz was informed of the criteria beforehand and provided with the rubric. That made him feel less worried during the testing process. Considering the participant's age (20 years old), the topic of

Internet was relevant and interesting to him. The provided short YouTube video gave him more ideas on the topic and he could give longer speech during the Part 2. At first, the idea of being video recorded did not appeal to Aziz and he asked not to do so. However, when explained that this will help the test results be more valid and reliable because the test will be graded by two teachers, he agreed to the idea and asked for the copy of the recoding.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is obvious that the assessment goes hand in hand with the learning outcomes (Biggs & Tang, 2011). According to Davidson and Lynch (2002), the specifications are teacher's guidelines that can help to design effective tasks that meet the requirements of assessment principles. Hence, it is very important to prepare the assessment task and especially the high stake tests with the clearly defined and written test specifications.

The key question in assessment is, "How do we know that someone has learnt?" (Jarvis, Holford, & Griffin, 2005, p. 157). Another issue that I realized was the importance of principles of language assessment. These principles help understand whether the test we give to students is efficient, culturally and thematically appropriate, useful. I have never considered all five discussed assessment principles during this session as important and useful as they actually are. Analyzing both existing and modified tests showed me that the doubting task of creation or modification of the test becomes more comprehensive and effective when practicality, reliability, validity, authenticity along with the washback are considered.

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